

A Novel High Efficiency High Step-up Interleaved Converter with Voltage Multiplier Circuit for a PV System

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Abstract- A high step-up converter is proposed for a photovoltaic system. A voltage multiplier used here provides high voltage gain without extreme duty cycle. The voltage multiplier is composed of a conventional boost converter and coupled inductors. An extra conventional boost converter is integrated into the first phase to achieve a considerably higher voltage conversion ratio. The two-phase configuration not only reduces the current stress through each power switch, but also constrains the input current ripple, which decreases the conduction losses of metal–oxide–semiconductor field-effect transistors (MOSFETs). It also functions as a clamp circuit which alleviates the voltage spikes across the power switches. So, the low-voltage-rated MOSFETs can be adopted for reductions of conduction losses and cost. Efficiency improves because the energy stored in leakage inductances is recycled to the output terminal.

Keywords- Boost–Fly back converter, High step-up, photovoltaic system, Voltage multiplier module.

I. INTRODUCTION

Renewable sources of energy are increasingly valued worldwide because of energy shortage and environmental contamination. Renewable energy systems generate low voltage output and thus, high step-up dc/dc converters are widely employed in many renewable energy applications, including fuel cells, wind power, and photovoltaic systems are expected to play an important role in future energy production. Such system transform light energy into electrical energy, and convert low voltage into high voltage via a step-up converter, which can convert energy into electricity using a grid-by-grid inverter or store energy into a battery set. Figure 1 shows a typical photovoltaic system that consists of a solar module, a high step up converter, a charge-discharge controller, a battery set, and an inverter.

Figure 1: Typical Photovoltaic System

Conventional step-up converters, such as the boost converter and flyback converter, cannot achieve a high step-up conversion with high efficiency because of the resistances of elements or leakage inductance. Thus, a modified boost-flyback converter was proposed. Modifying a boost-fly back converter, shown in Figure 2(a) is one of the simple approaches step-up gain and the gain is realized via a coupled inductor. The performance of the converter is similar to an active-clamped flyback converter; thus, the leakage energy is recovered to the output terminal. An interleaved boost converter with a voltage-lift capacitor shown in Figure 2(b) is highly similar to the conventional interleaved type. It obtains extra voltage gain through the voltage-lift capacitor, and reduces the input current ripple, which is suitable for power factor correction (PFC) and high-power applications.